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To cite this article: C P Zengler *et al* 2024 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **2767** 092066

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Further improvements to the double-Gaussian wake model

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Abstract. In onshore wind farms, the turbine-to-turbine distance can be in the order of three diameters or less. In these circumstances, traditional wake models, developed for the far wake region, lose accuracy. The double-Gaussian wake model is an approach to extend algebraic wake modelling to the near wake region, where the wake is not yet self-similar. In this work, the double-Gaussian wake model is advanced by performing large eddy simulations of a reference wind turbine and a scaled wind turbine model to investigate how the thrust coefficient and the turbulence intensity influence the near wake and wake recovery. Results show that in the near wake the maximum velocity deficits move towards the outer part of the rotor with an increasing thrust coefficient. Thus, a thrust coefficient dependent position of the double-Gaussian peaks is proposed. In addition, a wake expansion function including turbulence intensity and thrust coefficient is tuned. The new model proves to be capable of predicting the wake of different turbine models under various ambient conditions and operational states.

1. Introduction

The annual energy yield of a wind farm depends on meteorological boundary conditions, but also on the type and number of installed turbines and the flow aerodynamics within the farm. Depending on the ambient conditions and the turbine operating state, a wake is generated behind single turbines due to the extraction of momentum from the flow. Traveling downstream, the wake dissipates as momentum from the ambient flow is entrained into the wake. If not yet fully recovered, impinging wakes can significantly influence the power output of downstream turbines. An example is the onshore wind farm Dornum in northern Germany. This farm has a dense layout and the turbine spacing is in some cases less than three rotor diameters. As a result, the power production decreases by up to 80 % under some wind directions [1]. Besides the reduction in power output, also fatigue loads on the turbines increase [2].

Computational wake interaction tools, like FLORIS, allow to predict the flow within a plant [3]. They offer low computational cost by not physically resolving the entire flow field. Instead, wake deficits and added turbulence intensities are superimposed on a mean flow field by simple engineering descriptions. These models need to be sufficiently accurate in regions where other turbines are placed and fast enough to be applicable for optimization and control purposes. Historically, wake models were mainly developed for mid and far wake regions [4, 5, 6]. In these regimes, the wake reaches a self-similar state which simplifies the modelling process.

However, as demonstrated by the above example, turbines in onshore wind farms can be densely spaced. Therefore, it is necessary to develop models that are also accurate in the near wake region. Efforts in this direction have already been made, however – since the flow is not fully self-similar in this region – a generic representation is difficult [6, 7]. Ref. [8] acknowledges this by proposing a super-Gaussian function for the velocity deficit. Thus, the model takes on a more top-hat shape in the near wake before decaying to the known Gaussian function in the far wake. A more accurate description is proposed by double-Gaussian models [7, 9, 10]. These predict a lower velocity deficit in the wake core, as observed in computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and experimental studies [11]. However, the first studies did not offer insights into the driving effects that lead to the double peak shape. Thus, the derived models did not contain physical parametrizations, but were tuned to their respective validation case. Ref. [12] proposed to refine the model by introducing two separate decay functions in the horizontal and vertical directions, allowing for a non-circular wake outline. In [13], the authors further introduced a wake decay function based on the potential core theory [14].

The focus of the present study is to investigate the driving effects of the double-Gaussian wake shape from an engineering perspective. This is done through the analysis of several CFD simulations and experimental data. The developed parametrization allows for a more general application of the double-Gaussian wake model. The paper is organized as follows: the double-Gaussian wake model is presented in Sect. 2, while the CFD based on large-eddy simulation (LES) is presented in Sect. 3. Results are provided in Sect. 4.

2. Double-Gaussian wake model

In the following section, the existing formulation of the double-Gaussian wake model is presented first. Based on this, it is discussed how the position of the Gaussian peaks can be estimated. Furthermore, a new formulation to address wake expansion is proposed and last, an approximate way of calculating the initial wake width is presented.

The velocity deficit in the wake can be expressed as the product of an amplitude function $A(x)$ and a shape function $S(x, r)$

$$\frac{U_\infty - U_W}{U_\infty} = A(x)S(x, r), \quad (1)$$

where U represents the undisturbed mean flow, U_W the wake flow, and x and r are the axial and radial coordinates. All further equations and quantities are formulated in relative coordinates, normalized by the turbine diameter D . The shape function is formulated as the sum of two Gaussian bells [7, 9]

$$S(r, x) = \frac{1}{2} (e^{D^+} + e^{D^-}), \quad (2)$$

$$D_\pm(r) = -\frac{(r \pm r_0)^2}{2\sigma^2}, \quad (3)$$

where r_0 is the initial position of the Gaussian peaks, and σ the respective standard width.

The amplitude function $A(x)$ is derived from conservation of momentum [7, 9]. The approach by Keane [10] is adopted in this work, which overcomes the problem of complex solutions arising at high thrust coefficients by considering the modulus as a valid solution to the root function, therefore

$$A = \begin{cases} \frac{M - \sqrt{M^2 - \frac{1}{2}NC_T}}{2N}, & \text{if } M^2 - \frac{1}{2}NC_T \geq 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{M^2 + |M^2 - \frac{1}{2}NC_T|}}{2N}, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

with the thrust coefficient $C_T = \frac{T}{\frac{1}{2}\rho(\frac{D}{2})^2\pi U_\infty^2}$ and M and N defined as

$$M = 2\sigma^2 \exp\left(-\frac{r_0^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) + \sqrt{2\pi}r_0\sigma \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{r_0}{\sqrt{2}\sigma}\right), \quad (5)$$

$$N = \sigma^2 \exp\left(-\frac{r_0^2}{\sigma^2}\right) + \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{\pi}r_0\sigma \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{r_0}{\sigma}\right). \quad (6)$$

2.1. Initial peak position

The position of the double-Gaussian peaks was in previous works considered as a fixed value. Keane et al. [7] set $r_0 = 0.75 D/2$, Schreiber et al. [9] set $r_0 = 0.535 D/2$, and Soesanto et al. [12] $r_0 = 0.52 D/2$. Keane [10] fitted r_0 for different inflow velocities, and obtained values in a range between 0.3 and $0.6D/2$ for inflow velocities between 4 and 16 m s^{-1} . In this work, a more general approach is proposed, which relates the peak position with the thrust coefficient as

$$r_0 = 0.25 + 0.25 \tanh(a_1 + b_1 C_T), \quad (7)$$

where a_1 and b_1 are tuneable model parameters. This idea is motivated by the empirical observation that the wake shape varies depending on the operational state and thus the loading of the turbine blades, as it will be shown in Sect. 4. Indirectly, this approach is also inherent in the work by Keane [10]. However, the thrust coefficient for each of their fits is not reported and no general relation between turbine operating state and peak position is proposed.

2.2. Wake expansion functions

With a downstream expanding wake, the wake width σ needs to increase as well. The wake expansion is modelled as

$$\sigma = k_1 C_T^{k_2} I^{k_3} (x - x_0) + a_\epsilon \epsilon, \quad (8)$$

with the turbulence intensity $I = \frac{u'}{u}$, the initial wake width ϵ , the position of the initial wake width x_0 , and the tuneable parameters k_i and a_ϵ . This approach is inspired by [11] and assumes that both thrust coefficient and turbulence intensity have a non-linear, coupled influence on the wake expansion. The position x_0 of the initial wake width is set to $1 D$. This choice is motivated by two reasons. First, it was observed that the initial wake expansion region is approximately $1 D$ long [6, 15]. Second, in other works no consistent way of calculating x_0 could be identified. Schreiber et al. [9] assumed x_0 to be identical to the outlet of a Betz stream tube and fitted it to available data. Keane et al. [7] set it to zero while, in Soesanto et al. [12, 13], x_0 is determined from a semi-analytical relation. In this work, the introduction of the parameter a_ϵ yields a way of accounting for a mismatch between the initial wake position and the initial wake width.

2.3. Initial wake width calculation

Schreiber et al. [9] calculated the initial wake width ϵ by equating the mass flow of the double-Gaussian model with the one obtained from momentum theory at a given thrust coefficient at $x = x_0$ leading to the following implicit equation for ϵ

$$\frac{\beta}{8} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{2}{\beta} C_T}\right) = M \frac{M - \sqrt{M^2 - \frac{1}{2} N C_T}}{2N}, \quad (9)$$

with $\beta = \frac{1}{2} \frac{1 + \sqrt{1 - C_T}}{\sqrt{1 - C_T}}$. This equation needs to be solved numerically for every combination of C_T and r_0 . An approximate, empirical solution $\tilde{\epsilon}$ to this equation is proposed here, which reads

$$\tilde{\epsilon} = a_2 + b_2 e^{-\frac{r_0^2}{2c_2^2}} + 0.25\sqrt{\beta}, \quad (10)$$

with the tuned parameters $a_2 = -0.203$, $b_2 = 0.205$, and $c_2 = 0.208$. A comparison between the approximate and the exact solution is shown later in section 4.1.2.

3. LES

3.1. Set-up

LESs in combination with actuator line modelling (ALM) are performed. As turbines, the scaled wind turbine model G1 [16, 17] and the IEA 3.4 MW reference wind turbine [18] are used. The scaled model serves as a validation case of the simulation setup against experimental data, while the larger IEA 3.4 MW is chosen as a representation of modern onshore wind turbines. The ALM by [19] is used by running simulations with an in-house version of SOWFA (Simulator fOr Wind Farm Applications) [20], properly modified to reproduce the aerodynamics of scaled models [21]. In addition, for the IEA 3.4 MW, the filtered version of the ALM is implemented to account for a non-optimal kernel size [22]. In both cases, individual blades are resolved by 108 sampling points. The filter width in case of the G1 is 0.013 m and in case of the IEA 3.4 MW 1.1 m. Simulations are performed on a cartesian grid with progressive refinement layers. The finest mesh layer used is 1 m for the IEA 3.4 MW and 0.01 m for the G1. The domain for the simulation of the G1 is $14.4 \times 4 \times 3.5 D^3$ in x , y , and z directions respectively, corresponding to the streamwise, lateral, and vertical coordinates, with the turbine located $2.9D$ behind the inlet. In case of the IEA 3.4 MW, the domain extends to $15 \times 5 \times 3.5 D^3$ and the turbine is placed $4D$ downstream from the inlet. Furthermore, the nacelle and tower are fully resolved and meshed with the *snappyHexMesh* utility [23]. To assess the influence of the mesh resolution around nacelle and tower, three different meshes, with an increasing level of refinement, were compared for the G1. In all cases, the resulting mean velocity profiles in the wake were very similar, so all meshes were considered as suitable. The medium refined mesh is used in the following if not stated otherwise. Its properties and the one of the mesh of the IEA 3.4 MW, which was obtained using similar algorithm settings, are summarized in Tab. 1. A wall function

Table 1. Properties of medium refined G1 mesh and the IEA 3.4 MW mesh. Obtained from OpenFOAM with the *checkMesh* utility.

	G1	IEA 3.4 MW
Cells	1.424×10^7	2.326×10^7
Hexahedra	1.410×10^7	2.306×10^7
Prisms	8.716×10^3	1.022×10^4
Polyhedras	1.371×10^5	1.837×10^5
Max aspect ratio	3.11	3.75
Max non-orthogonality	29.86	33.76
Max skewness	0.88	1.16
Min volume [m ³]	4.56×10^{-9}	2.56×10^{-3}

is used on nacelle and tower. The average y^+ is 29.52 for the G1 mesh. At the top, side, and bottom, slip boundary conditions are imposed. In case of the IEA 3.4 MW, no-slip conditions in combination with a wall function are imposed on the bottom boundary.

Inflow conditions are obtained using either precursor simulations or synthetic turbulence generation. The inflow for the G1 is obtained from a simulation of the boundary layer wind tunnel of Politecnico di Milano conducted by [24]. In addition, a uniform inflow is simulated. A neutral atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) is simulated for the IEA 3.4 MW. Further, for this turbine, synthetic inflow profiles are generated with TurbSim [25] with the spatial coherence modified according to [26]. Inflow properties consisting of wind speed at hub height U_∞ , turbulence intensity I_∞ and shear exponent α are summarized in Tab. 2.

Table 2. Properties of the applied inflow profiles.

Turbine	Inflow type	U_∞ [m s ⁻¹]	I_∞ [-]	α [-]
G1	precursor of wind tunnel	5.77	0.06	0.11
G1	uniform	5.80	0.00	0.00
IEA 3.4 MW	synthetic	9.78	0.06	0.12
IEA 3.4 MW	synthetic	9.80	0.01	0.12
IEA 3.4 MW	synthetic	12.40	0.11	0.12
IEA 3.4 MW	precursor of neutral ABL	10.84	0.06	0.12
IEA 3.4 MW	precursor of neutral ABL	10.77	0.04	0.07
IEA 3.4 MW	precursor of neutral ABL	10.52	0.11	0.15

Figure 1. Validation of the LES setup with experimental and numerical results from [24]. **a)** mean velocity at hub height and **b)** turbulence intensity.

3.2. Validation

The LES setup is validated for the scaled G1 turbine with experimental and numerical data available from a measurement campaign conducted at the boundary layer wind tunnel of Politecnico di Milano by [24]. Results are shown in Fig. 1. In general, the LES results resemble the measurement data well. It can be noticed that a slight asymmetry with respect to the x -axis in the experimental data exists. Furthermore, the results tend to slightly overpredict the velocity deficit. But comparing the velocity profiles at the wake boundaries, it becomes apparent, that the reference velocity U_∞ might be lower in the experimental case, leading to a generally shifted velocity profile. Inspecting the turbulence intensity in 1 **b)**, it can be observed that, especially at 1.4D, the simulation results agree well with the experimental data. The higher accuracy, especially in the wake core, compared to the simulations by [24], can be explained by the application of different modelling approaches of the tower and nacelle. In this work, body-conformal meshing is applied, while in [24], the immersed boundary method is used. Since the simulation setup is capable of accurately reproducing the flow features in the near wake, it is concluded that it is suitable for the development of a near-wake model.

Figure 2. Position of the radial velocity minimum for varying C_T at **a)** 1 D, and **b)** 4 D behind the turbine. Marker colors indicate turbulence intensity at hub height, respectively. Fitted coefficients of (7) are $a_1 = -1.90$ and $b_1 = 2.59$. Data from [27, 11, 9].

4. Results

4.1. Wake model

The free parameters of the wake model are fitted in two steps; first, Eq. (7) describing the initial peak position is fitted to available data and second, the wake expansion function (8) and thus the remaining free parameters are identified.

4.1.1. Peak position function In Fig. 2, the radial position of the wake velocity minima for varying C_T is visualized at two positions downstream of the turbine. In panel **a)**, at 1 D behind the turbine, a correlation between C_T and the minima can be observed. With an increasing C_T , the minima tend to move towards the outer part of the rotor. Moving downstream, this correlation becomes less clear. However, at 4 D, a dependency of the peak position on turbulence intensity I emerges. With an increasing I , the peak positions are found closer to the wake center, which can be explained by the increased mixing and thus wake recovery due to the higher turbulence levels.

In the light of the double-Gaussian wake model, the observation of velocity minima moving towards the outer part of the wake with an increasing C_T motivate the proposal of the C_T -dependent Gaussian peaks introduced in Sect. 2.1. In Fig. 2 **a)**, also a fit of function (7) is shown, which does not closely match single data points, but yields a general approximation of the correlation between thrust coefficient and velocity minimum. The data in the first subplot actually suggests that turbine-dependent trends might exist, which for the sake of generality are not considered here. The dependency of the peak position on I in the far wake stresses the need to include I in the modelling of the wake recovery expressed by the wake expansion function, which was proposed in Sect. 2.2.

4.1.2. Initial wake width calculation The tuned version of Eq. (7) can now be used in combination with the proposed approximate solution (10) for the calculation of the initial wake width. The approximation $\bar{\epsilon}$ together with the exact, numerical solution ϵ obtained from Eq. (9) is shown Fig. 3. As it can be seen, in the present case, the approximate solution resembles the numerical solution very closely and is therefore used within this work.

4.1.3. Wake expansion function Next, the wake expansion function (8) is fitted to the LES data available for the IEA 3.4 MW and the G1 model wind turbine at 1, 3, and 6 D. Results are shown in Tab. 3. The parameter, which scales C_T is set to zero, which appears inconsistent because also in a situation of no turbulence intensity, shear induced turbulent mixing eventually leads to wake recovery. This might be explained by a bias in the data used for tuning not including

Figure 3. Calculation of the initial wake width: ϵ based on numerical solution proposed by [9] and $\tilde{\epsilon}$ based on (10). In both cases, r_0 is calculated from the tuned Eq. (7).

Table 3. Summary of tuneable model functions (7), (8), and (10).

Function	Parameters
$\sigma = k_1 C_T^{k_2} I^{k_3} (x - x_0) + a_\epsilon \epsilon$	$k_1 = 0.073, k_2 = 0, k_3 = 0.585, a_\epsilon = 1.086$
$r_0 = 0.25 + 0.25 \tanh(a_1 + b_1 C_T)$	$a_1 = -1.90, b_1 = 2.59$
$\tilde{\epsilon} = a_2 + b_2 e^{-\frac{r_0^2}{2c_2^2}} + 0.25\sqrt{\beta}$	$a_2 = -0.203, b_2 = 0.205, c_2 = 0.208$

a sufficient amount of data points resembling the role of C_T sufficiently arcuate. Furthermore, in the investigated cases, I might be the driving factor influencing wake recovery at most of the distances used for fitting. The parameter a_ϵ is set to nearly one which indicates that $x_0 = 1$ D might be a good choice for the initial wake position. In Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, the resulting model and the corresponding LES data for the G1 and the IEA 3.4 MW are shown in the horizontal plane at hubheight for C_T between 0.35 and 0.79 and I between 0.01 and 0.11. For comparison, the model by Schreiber et al. [9] is shown as well. In Fig. 4 **a**) it can be observed that the amplitude of the velocity minimum is correctly predicted at nearly all downstream positions, although the peak in the wake center – especially directly behind the turbine – is not resolved. Fig. 4 **b**) shows that the faster wake recovery in comparison to **a**) due to a higher turbulence level is correctly predicted by the new model. In Fig. 4 **c**) and Fig 5 I is similar, so the only difference is C_T and different turbines. The new model predicts a rather single-Gaussian velocity deficit in the near wake in **c**), although a double-Gaussian deficit is present in the LES data, which can be explained by the generic fit of (7) to the data in Fig. 2 **a**). It is apparent, that a turbine-specific fit would likely yield better predictions. In Fig. 5, the new model correctly predicts a single-Gaussian velocity deficit at low C_T and a double-Gaussian deficit at high C_T . However, the wake recovery rate appears to be overpredicted at low C_T .

4.2. Validation

Finally, the new model is validated with experimental and LES data from other authors. Ishihara and Qian [11] performed LES of an actuator disc resembling a 2.4 MW offshore turbine with a rotor diameter of 92 m under varying conditions at a mean wind speed at 10.2 m s^{-1} and a force distribution calculated with blade element theory. Krogstad and Adaramola [27] investigated a scaled wind turbine model with a diameter of 0.9 m at mean wind speed of 10 m s^{-1} at low I

Figure 4. LES results and predictions by the proposed model and by the model by [9] for the IEA 3.4 MW for $C_T = 0.79, 0.78, 0.58$ and $I = 0.01, 0.11, 0.06$. Distances 1, 3, and 6 D were used for model tuning, marked by *.

Figure 5. LES results and predictions by the proposed model and by the model by [9] for the G1 for $C_T = 0.75, 0.35$ and $I = 0.06$. Distances 1, 3, and 6 D were used for model tuning, marked by *.

(< 0.01). Model predictions are shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, respectively. It must be noted, that for the tuning of $r_0(C_T)$ also data from [27] was used. From both figures, it can be observed that the new model predicts the approximate shape of the velocity deficit consistently. With a decreasing thrust coefficient, also the distance of the double-Gaussian peaks from the centerline decreases. In case of the LES data, at low C_T s (Fig. 6 a), c), the wake recovery rate appears to be overpredicted, which is consistent with the findings presented in the previous section.

Figure 6. Validation of the proposed model with numerical results from Ishihara and Qian [11] for $C_T = 0.36, 0.84$ and $I = 0.04, 0.14$.

Figure 7. Validation of the proposed model with experimental results from Krogstad and Adaramola [27] for $C_T = 0.47, 0.85$ and $I = 0.01$.

Conversely, at high C_T s (Fig. 6 b), d), the amplitude of the velocity deficit is underpredicted in the near wake. Comparing the wind tunnel measurements with the respective predictions (Fig. 7), a very good agreement can be seen. However, in Fig. 7 b) at 4D, the wake recovery appears to be underpredicted. The reason for this is the low turbulence intensity. The wake recovery in the analytical model is nearly zero in these cases. However, in the experiments, rotor-induced turbulence – which is linked to the thrust coefficient – leads to a recovery of the wake. This effect is not present in the new wake model, because the parameter regulating the influence of C_T on recovery is zero as well. However, it should be noted that ambient turbulence intensity levels of $I < 0.01$ are rather rare, especially onshore [28], thus in practice, a wake recovery purely due to rotor-induced turbulence is very unlikely.

5. Conclusions

An extension of the double-Gaussian wake model is proposed, which incorporates a thrust coefficient-dependent position of the Gaussian peaks. The model predicts an increasing distance of the peaks from the centerline with an increasing thrust coefficient. Comparing the model predictions with LES data and results from other authors, a relatively accurate agreement is observed. In most cases, the proposed parametrization predict well the influence of thrust coefficient on the peak positions and the influence of turbulence intensity on wake recovery. Nevertheless, modelling challenges still remain in the near wake, that can be addressed in future

works. For instance, in this region, the exact velocity distribution is blade-specific, since the velocity deficit also depends on the local loading of the blades. Furthermore, on the edges of the wake and on the centerline, the strong velocity gradients cannot be reproduced by the double-Gaussian wake model. A solution to this issue could be to include the super-Gaussian formulation [8] in the double-Gaussian model.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank Professor Carlo L. Bottasso for initiating the research question and for the constructive comments and suggestions. This work has been partially supported by the MERIDIONAL project, which receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under the grant agreement No. 101084216.

Furthermore, the authors express their gratitude to the Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ) for providing access and computing time on the SuperMUC Petascale System under the project-ID pr84be "Large-eddy Simulation for Wind Farm Control".

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